

Enhancing Trust, Integrity and Efficiency in Research through next-level Reproducibility

ORRG

Open Science in Qualitative Research: Challenges and Enablers

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About Me (positionality statement)

- Qualitative sociologist with a focus on systems of power and inequality
 - Power and knowledge formation (sociology of knowledge)
- Metascientist focused on science reform policy and practices, equity issues, epistemic diversity, and impacts
 - Open Science, reproducibility, Responsible Research and Innovation
- Open Science "newbie"; conflicted stance
- Believe in the value of openness

How I Understand Open Science

"Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields **accessible to everyone** for the **benefits of scientists and society** as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that **the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable.**" -- UNESCO

<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about>

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, 2021.

Why I Believe in Open Science

- Practicing Open Science has improved the rigor, transparency, and quality of my work
- Have seen and generated the evidence of Open Science impact in the PathOS project (<https://pathos-project.eu/>)
- Open Science practices and infrastructures drive:
 - Academic impact: quality, efficiency and productivity, equity, diversity and inclusion ([Klebel et al. 2025](#))
 - Societal impact: equity, empowerment, climate & environment, health & safety ([Cole et al. 2024](#))
 - Economic impact: economic growth and innovation ([Tsipouri et al. 2025](#))
- ***Yet not all Open Science practices are appropriate for all research in all cases***

Our Roadmap

- Context
- Review study design, methods and Open Science practices
- High-level findings (sample characteristics)
- In-depth findings about challenges and enablers
- Implications
- Conclusions and next steps

The Context

Enhancing Trust, Integrity
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Qualitative research at the margins

Highest prevalence by field of qualitative methods in Scopus title, keyword and abstract in 2019 (%)

[Source: Thelwall and Nevill, 2021. "Is research with qualitative data more prevalent and impactful now?" *Library & Information Science Research*, 43\(2\).](#)

Qualitative research at the margins of Open Science

- Open Science has been institutionalized (policy, funding, publishing) in ways that center open outputs (products) – data sets and OA publications
- A study of global Open Science policy documents published between 2020 and 2022 found that policy actions overwhelmingly focus on implementing and increasing Open Access publishing, open data, and open infrastructures ([Chtena et al. 2025](#))
- Open data practices and expectations, and related practices have been driven by and for quantitative research epistemologies and methods
- Many in the qualitative research community experience and report a mismatch between established Open Science practices, norms and expectations, and *their* epistemologies and ethical commitments

Study Design

Examining the relationship between Open Science and qualitative research

RQ1: How are reproducibility and replication conceptualized and discussed in relation to qualitative research?

RQ2: Which factors and practices enable, and which are barriers to, the potential reproducibility or replication of qualitative research?

Reproducibility and replicability of qualitative research:
an integrative review of concepts, barriers and enablers

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Author contributions

Conceptualization (NLC, SU, AB, MG, BL, TRH); data curation (NLC, EK); formal analysis (NLC, SU, AB, MG, EK); funding acquisition (TRH); investigation (NLC, SU, AB, MG, BL, TRH); methodology (NLC, SU, AB, MG, EK, TRH); project administration (NLC); resources (TRH); software (EK); supervision (NLC, TRH); validation (NLC, SU); writing (original draft) (NLC, SU, EK, AB); writing (editing and review) (NLC, SU, EK, AB, MG, TRH, BL).

Abstract

The integrative review presented here examines how reproducibility and replicability are conceptualized and discussed in relation to qualitative research, and which factors and practices enable or undermine them. Both peer-reviewed and grey English-language literature that address reproducibility and/or Open Science in relation to qualitative research were eligible for inclusion. Initial searches were conducted in Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions, PubMed, APA PsychInfo, and JSTOR, and followed with snowball sampling from included literature. Studies were screened and both quantitative and qualitative data were extracted using the SyRF online platform, with 248 papers included. We found that conceptualizations that stem from quantitative standpoints are overwhelmingly framed as inappropriate practices and epistemic criteria for (most) qualitative research. When conceptualized in alternative ways that are adapted

High Level Findings

A

248 Sources

130 Publication Outlets

704 Authors*

*29 with ≥ 3 contributions

B

C

General Qualitative Research (35.5%)

Medical and Health Sciences (16.9%)

Psychology (13.3%)

Political Science (9.7%)

Social Sciences (8.5%)

Economics and Business (2.8%)

Education (2.8%)

Other (10.5%)

Challenges to Open Qualitative Research

Challenges to Open Science for Qualitative Research

Coding query result for barriers to Open Science practices, number of coding instances shown

Ontological and Epistemological Challenges

"[Open Science] tends to ignore some of the most basic principles upon which qualitative research is founded." (Slavnic 2013)

"Open science approaches and practices have been developed in response to challenges in quantitative research (such as the replicability crisis), and with quantitative research methods and data in mind. What many qualitative researchers have in common is that they face pressures to comply with practices and guidelines associated with open science not designed with our prominent research approaches, methods, and data types in mind." (Prosser et al. 2022)

Challenges to Specific Open Science Practices

Challenges to Open Qualitative Data Practices

Ethical Challenges

- “...it could be argued that the imperatives of open science may at times directly oppose and prevent researchers from being able to act in accordance with their research ethics of accountability and treat their participants’ data with consideration and care.” (Prosser et al. 2022)
- “researchers’ ethical obligations to protect human participants and their communities ought to take priority over the sharing of information with research consumers.” (Jacobs et al. 2021)

Anonymity, Consent and Context as Challenges

Anonymity

- Risk of reidentification
- Anonymization is challenging and costly
- Full deidentification may render shared data unusable

Consent

- Established trust is not transferrable
- One-off consent is not universal consent
- Reuse may breach established trust and intended use

Context

- Lack of field immersion by secondary researcher
- Archived data are detached from context

“The last thing that racialized, marginalized, poor/working-class folks, dis/abled people, LGBTQIA[+] persons, and folk at the intersections of these diverse groups need is more research about them, without them.” (Guishard, 2018)

Yet Open Qualitative Research is Thriving!

The Qualitative Data Repository

Search data...

Discover Data

Just Getting Started
Learn more about QDR
Browse Guidance

QRS 2025: Transparency, Openness and Qualitative Research

28 JAN 2025 9.00am

10 East, University of Bath

Ninth Annual Qualitative Research Symposium (QRS).

A poster for the "Symposium | OPEN SCIENCE IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH" held on 25 September 2025 at the University of Antwerp Stadscampus. The poster features a central graphic of six stylized faces in a 2x3 grid. Surrounding the faces are names and topics: "dr. Olivier Boehme FWO | FUNDING THE FUTURE FWO", "Prof. dr. Charlotte De Backer ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS UAntwerpen", "dr. Nicki Lisa Cole BARRIERS & ENABLERS Know Center Research Austria", "Bea Mertens AUDIT TRAILING UAntwerpen", "Linde Tuybens CLOSED TO OPEN DATA UAntwerpen", and "dr. Tamarinde Haven PRE-REGISTRATION Tilburg University".

A screenshot of the OSF Registries website showing a dark blue button labeled "Add New Registration". Above the button are navigation links: "OSF REGISTRIES", "Add New", "My Registrations", "Help", and "Donate".

A snippet of the OSF registration form. It includes a question: "Do you want to register in an existing OSF project?" with "YES" and "NO" radio button options. Below it is another question: "Which project do you want to register? *".

A blue event banner for "Sharing Sensitive Qualitative Data". It features a portrait of a woman on the right. Text on the banner includes "CENTER FOR OPEN SCIENCE", "Feb. 15 // 11 am ET", and "Sharing Sensitive Qualitative Data".

Rebecca Carr
Moderated by

Enablers of Open Qualitative Research

Enablers of Open Qualitative Research

Qualitative Research Practices as Enablers of Open Science (# of coded texts)

Fostering Openness with Qualitative Research Practices

- Field notes & thick description --> register context information, create data collection and analytic transparency and support data reuse
- Code books, coding process, and software information --> analytic transparency
- Reflexivity --> identify assumptions, biases and values and their role on data gathering and analysis, provide process transparency
- Audit trails --> methodological and analytic transparency

Conclusions

Conclusions

- Qualitative research approaches, methods and practices can be framed as challenges to Open Science, or as enablers of it
- The quantitatively driven design of Open Science norms, practices and services is a key challenge to Open Qualitative Research
- A lack of epistemic diversity in science reform is the foundation of key challenges

Epistemic Diversity Improves Open Science

"Feminist and qualitative scholars have long maintained that there are multiple ways of understanding, yet evangelists of the open science movement have commonly made assumptions that there is a shared understanding of a specific type of research (e.g., empiricism, deductive reasoning). This problematic assumption ***halts progress in the integration of perspectives for open science*** and contributes to possibly ignoring systematically marginalized voices (see Bennett et al., 2022)" (Steltenpohl et al. 2023).

Conclusions

- Established qualitative research practices can foster the expansion of and strengthen Open Methods and Open Analysis, and help maximize the value of Open Data
- Qualitative research practices can enhance, enrich and expand Open Science

Thank you
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Next Steps

Join the European OQR Community

- What? An Open Qualitative Researcher Community focused on the European research, funding and policy landscape
- Why? To foster support, collaboration, debate and discussion, to share resources to support ethical and appropriate openness and transparency, and to influence science policy in a coordinated way
- Status: community in formation with over 300 members
- Sign up to join in here:

Join us on LinkedIn

Workshop: Pre-registration in Qualitative Research

- Led by Dr. Tamarinde Haven
- Explore how an open science practice, preregistration, can be useful for you in making your work more rigorous and transparent
- However... What does a rigorous preregistration mean?
- All are welcome to become familiar with considerations for qualitative preregistration and to explore rigour together!

Q & A

References

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- [Thelwall and Nevill, 2021. "Is research with qualitative data more prevalent and impactful now?" Library & Information Science Research, 43\(2\).](#)